

Book of Abstracts

**COST Action
FP1407
Final Conference**

**LIVING
WITH
MODIFIED
WOOD**

Belgrade, Serbia
12-13 December 2018

University of Belgrade – Faculty of Forestry

COST Action FP1407

Understanding wood modification through an integrated scientific and environmental impact approach (ModWoodLife)

Living with modified wood

Final COST Action FP1407 International Conference

Belgrade, Serbia, 12 – 13th December 2018

Book of Abstracts

Editors: Goran Milić, Nebojša Todorović, Tanja Palijsa, Andreja Kutnar

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Local organiser preface

It is both a pleasure and a privilege for the Department of Technologies, Management and Design of Furniture and Wood Products, Faculty of Forestry to host the final conference of COST Action FP1407. This honour has given us an opportunity to establish a more visible position within the European network of wood related institutions.

Wording of the title - “Living with modified wood” - signifies that the time in which we live has provided us with technologies of wood modification that will ensure that never again will this material be regarded as a lesser material with a short life-span. Wood, as one of the rare living materials, is experiencing a worldwide renaissance, one that could not have been considered possible just a generation ago. For these very reasons, the primary goal of this conference is to foster, forge and encourage the cooperation and exchange of ideas between wood modification researchers and experts in related fields and, hopefully, help them grow.

Belgrade, as a city with a long and rather eventful history, is an environment where sparse moments of peace and prosperity have instilled a way of thinking that appreciates the little things in life. This setting emphasises even more the pressing need of the modern age to live more organically, ethically and above all, ecologically – and what better way than living with an organic material such as wood.

Success of this event would not have been possible without the effort of the entire team of my colleagues. I would like to thank them and to express my deepest gratitude to Andreja Kutnar, Chair of COST FP1407, for leading this fantastic Action, and for her continuous help in organising this Final Conference.

Last but not least I would like to thank all of the participants and contributors of the Final COST FP1407 Conference. I wish you to have a memorable time in Belgrade.

So let us look forward to an exciting conference!

Goran Milić

Preface

Welcome to the fourth and final international conference of COST Action FP1407 “Understanding wood modification through an integrated scientific and environmental impact approach” (ModWoodLife). This conference, “Living with modified wood”, held in Belgrade, Serbia December 12 and 13, 2018 brings researchers and professionals together to share and disseminate their work. Their research contributes significantly to our Action’s objectives. It is especially rewarding too see contributions that have resulted from collaborations developed and strengthened through this network. Since the beginning of the Action in 2015, we have delivered new knowledge in the field of wood modification and environmental impact assessment. We can all be proud that during our Action, the European Union recognized the need to strategically approach activities, research, and policy to reduce climate change. Among the key strategies that were accepted in the past three years are the Circular Economy (2015), the Paris Agreement (2016), the Research and Innovation Roadmap 2050 – A Sustainable and Competitive Future for European Raw Materials (2018), as well as the recently renewed Bioeconomy strategy. Although our Action did not directly contribute to these documents, I am convinced that the activities of our network and its participants accelerated their adoption. At the same time, it is clear that our collaboration must continue after the Action ends on March 9, 2019. Going forward we should jointly contribute to “closing the loop” of product lifecycles through greater recycling and re-use and bring benefits for both the environment and the economy.

I would like to thank you for your great collaboration. Besides the new knowledge we created, our new friendships will continue for many years more!

Wishing you a successful and memorable conference in Belgrade.

Andreja Kutnar
Chair, COST FP1407

Can modified wood compete with untreated wood in preference of people?

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Visual or tactile contact with pleasant materials can improve our affective states and decrease our physiological arousal. Accordingly, pleasant materials may have a protective or restorative role in human stress responses. Current evidence suggests that tactile and visual contact with wood leads to healthier affective and physiological outcomes when compared to other common materials (Burnard and Kutnar 2015, Demattè *et al.* 2018, Ikei *et al.* 2017). Recently, however, modified wood has become widespread due to its improved properties, such as enhanced durability and dimensional stability (Sandberg *et al.* 2017). Importantly, these changes are accompanied by alterations of the material’s visual and tactile qualities (Bakar *et al.* 2013), which influence human perception and evaluation of materials. Is modified wood, with its visual and tactile changes, still liked among people when compared to untreated wood? Are some modification processes better than others in creating appealing materials?

To gain insight into these questions, we prepared 30 wood samples (approximately 7 x 15 x 1 cm) from several species that are either untreated or treated (i.e., thermally modified, chemically modified, impregnated, coated, or treated with a combination of these methods) (Fig. 1). As a first step, a group of experts rated all samples based on several sensory (e.g., glossy, dark) and evaluative (e.g., natural) attributes. After completing this step, we conducted the study in two phases. First, we presented all 30 samples to 25 participants simultaneously and asked them to choose their favourite five materials to be used as an outdoor table top surface based on their combined tactile and visual inspection (and rank these five favourite materials from their most to least favourite). From the initial group of 30 materials, we selected 10 samples that on average received the highest rankings. These 10 samples were then ranked by a new group of 50 participants, similarly as in the first phase.

The presented results will demonstrate how modified wood fares against untreated wood in terms of preference. In addition, we will present associations between preference rankings, wood modification processes, wood species, as well as sensory and evaluative attributes of wood.

Figure 1: Wood samples used in the study.

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